

Real-World Performance of Amniotic Membrane Allografts for Chronic Wounds: Multi-Site Results from a Retrospective EHR Study

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Abstract

Background: Chronic wounds, including diabetic foot ulcers, venous leg ulcers, and pressure ulcers, affect large and clinically complex populations, driving infection, hospitalization, limb loss, diminished quality of life, and substantial health system costs. Although randomized and observational studies suggest benefit of amniotic membrane allografts, real-world performance remains uncertain because routine-care populations differ from trial cohorts, standard-of-care varies across sites, and documentation is heterogeneous. Transparent, prespecified estimates under routine practice, produced with auditable definitions, privacy safeguards, and feasibility checks for bias-controlled comparative analyses, are needed to inform clinical use and payer coverage decisions

Objective: To report real-world benchmarks for healing and complications among patients treated with amniotic membrane allografts and to assess feasibility for the prespecified bias-controlled comparative analyses.

Design, Setting, and Participants: Multi-site, retrospective cohort study using de-identified electronic health records from U.S. wound care practices. Analyses were performed against a prespecified data-lock date. Adults (≥ 18 years) with diabetic foot, venous leg, or pressure ulcers were eligible per protocol. For treated patients, Time 0 (index date) was the first allograft application.

Exposure: Incident use of a study amniotic membrane allograft in addition to routine care.

Main Outcomes and Measures: Primary outcome: complete closure of the index wound by Day 84 (Week 12) with confirmation within 60 days. Secondary outcomes: time-to-closure; $\geq 50\%$ wound-area reduction at approximately 4 weeks.

Results: Data from 2 sites yielded 904 eligible patients. and 109 patients total were included across all three treatment groups. By wound type, counts were DFU (29), VLU (17), and PU (63). Across six product-indication combinations (three amniotic membrane allograft products and three wound types, with several combinations occurring too infrequently to draw statistics), Day 84 closure was achieved in the range of 36.4-36.4% for DFU, 10.2-22.9% for PU, and 5.3-17.4% for VLU. These results are contextualized by a highly complex, comorbid real-world study population.

Conclusions and Relevance: These real-world benchmarks provide clinically interpretable estimates of healing under routine care and supply feasibility evidence, including overlap, balance, and effective sample size diagnostics, to guide the definitive bias-controlled comparative analyses and inform clinical use and coverage considerations as the program progresses.

Trial Registration: ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT Number - NCT07223281

Keywords: Amniotic membrane allograft; diabetic foot ulcer; venous leg ulcer; pressure ulcer; real-world evidence; EHR.

Introduction

Chronic wounds, including diabetic foot ulcers (DFU), venous leg ulcers (VLU), and pressure ulcers (PU), are common, frequently recurrent, and medically complex. They are associated with infection, hospitalization, limb loss, reduced quality of life, and high costs to patients and health systems [1]. Clinical guidance emphasizes optimization of patient comorbidities and standard wound care (e.g. offloading for DFU, compression for VLU, and pressure redistribution for PU), yet healing is often challenging and variable across settings^[1-5].

Amniotic membrane allografts are used as adjuncts to standard care based on barrier, anti-inflammatory, and pro-healing properties. Randomized trials and meta-analyses in DFU and VLU generally report higher probabilities of closure and shorter time-to-closure with amniotic products versus standard care alone, although effect sizes vary with baseline wound severity, duration, and practice protocols^[6-12]. Real-world studies suggest similar benefits but are heterogeneous in design, outcome definitions, and approaches to confounding control^[13,14]. Transparent, prespecified estimates of performance under routine care can inform clinical decision-making and coverage policy^[15].

Electronic health records (EHRs) enable evaluation of treatment performance in practice, but observational analyses are vulnerable to selection bias, immortal-time bias, confounding by indication, and information bias due to variable documentation density and practice. Regulatory and methodological guidance for real-world data (RWD) and real-world evidence (RWE) underscores prespecification, data quality assessment, traceability, auditable variable definitions, alignment of index dates between treated and comparator groups, and feasibility assessments for causal estimation, together with target-trial and estimand frameworks to clarify the causal question and analysis population^[16-24].

This manuscript reports the real-world data analysis from a multi-site, retrospective EHR program. The prespecified primary endpoint is complete closure of the index wound by Day 84 (Week 12) with confirmation within 60 days. Secondary endpoints include time-to-closure and $\geq 50\%$ reduction in wound area at approximately 4 weeks. The study objectives are descriptive and feasibility-oriented: (i) to provide wound-type-specific benchmarks for healing, time-to-closure, early improvement, and complications among patients treated with amniotic membrane allografts under routine care; (ii) to characterize the real-world population used in future interim analyses and the final study, which is likely much more complex and heterogeneous compared to populations used in RCT, helping to contextualize results. Taken together, these outputs are intended to deliver estimates useful to decision-making while reducing risk for the confirmatory analyses that follow.

Methods

Setting and participants

Adults (≥ 18 years) with diabetic foot ulcers (DFU), venous leg ulcers (VLU), or pressure ulcers (PU) were eligible per prespecified inclusion/exclusion and observability criteria. For treated patients, Time 0 (index date) was the first documented application of a study amniotic membrane allograft.

Exposure

The exposure was incident use of a study amniotic membrane allograft in addition to routine care.

Outcomes

The primary outcome was complete closure of the index wound by Day 84 (Week 12).

Secondary outcomes were: (i) time-to-closure; (ii) $\geq 50\%$ reduction in wound area at approximately 4 weeks.

Covariates and assessment windows

The covariate set was prespecified based on well-established determinants of wound healing and known confounders of treatment–outcome relationships in wound care. These variables support design-stage procedures (control indexing; matching/coarsening), model-based adjustment, feasibility diagnostics, and generalizability profiling.

Domains and variables

- Demographics and location: age (years at index), sex; clinical site identifier.
- Wound-specific: wound area (cm²; length × width) on index date; wound duration (days); DFU Wagner grade and PU NPIAP stage; deepest exposed tissue for VLU; infection within 30 days prior to index.
- Comorbidities/clinical status: diabetes; peripheral arterial disease (PAD); venous insufficiency; chronic kidney disease; cardiovascular disease; peripheral neuropathy; malignancy; depression; ambulatory status; living status, smoking status; body mass index.
- Laboratory measurements (most recent at index): HbA1c, albumin, ankle–brachial index (for DFU), C-reactive protein, hemoglobin, creatinine.

- Medications (within 30 days prior to index): corticosteroids, immunosuppressants, antidiabetic agents, chemotherapy agents, anticoagulants.

Timing windows were: Day 0 for index wound measures; –30 to 0 days for recent infection and medications; and up to –180 to 0 days for comorbidities and labs. These covariates and assessment windows were selected a priori based on clinical guidelines and empirical evidence describing prognostic importance and confounding potential for wound healing outcomes.

Data acquisition, de-identification, harmonization, and lineage

Data from participating wound-care sites were securely transferred from source EHR systems to a centralized, HIPAA-compliant research platform (Droice Hawk) under data use agreements and site governance. Transfers were performed with integrity checks, encrypted transfer and storage, and restricted role-based access. Deidentification was applied prior to all analysis. No conversion to an external common data model (CDM) was performed; data were harmonized to a prespecified common study schema specific to this protocol.

Harmonization and variable derivation combined structured EHR elements (demographics, diagnoses, procedures, medications, laboratory results) with information derived from unstructured clinical notes using natural language processing; mapping leveraged code sets (e.g., ICD-10-CM, CPT/HCPCS, NDC, SNOMED) and controlled vocabularies defined for the study.

Traceability was maintained using Droice SuperLineage, which recorded lossless source-to-analysis lineage for every derived field and dataset, including extract identifiers, transformation scripts, and harmonization steps. The lineage enables atomic, data point level traceback of analysis data to the original source record, supporting source data verification and validation of key variables (e.g., exposure identity/date; outcome confirmation; covariate confirmation).

Quality safeguards within the pipeline encompassed completeness, conformance to time anchors, plausibility (e.g., closure cannot precede index), and cross-source consistency checks between structured fields and documentation-derived variables; discrepancies triggered adjudication according to prespecified procedures.

Statistical analysis

Analysis sets and stratification

Analyses were stratified by wound type (DFU, VLU, PU). The analysis set comprised eligible patients receiving an allograft at Time 0.

Treated performance benchmarks (single-arm)

In the dataset, the proportion healed by Day 84 was estimated overall and by wound type with exact (Clopper–Pearson) 95% CIs. Time-to-closure was summarized by plotting wound area trajectories. Early improvement endpoints were summarized as proportions with exact 95% CIs.

In clinical practice, it is common for participants to A) be lost to follow-up or B) discontinue participation following wound closure. To address these patterns of missing data, a complete case analysis was employed, which was restricted to wounds with an ascertainable 12-week outcome (either confirmed closure or documented as open at or post 12 weeks). This analysis may better represent real-world product performance, as patients frequently discontinue follow-up after wound healing has occurred.

Statistical software and reproducibility

Analyses were performed in R and Python. All transformations from source to analysis datasets were version-controlled with auditable lineage; outputs reference the data-lock date, dataset/version identifiers, and analysis-code tag/commit.

Results

Study population

Across 2 participating sites, 904 unique adults met eligibility criteria and 109 patients total were included in one of the three treatment groups across all three treatment groups. By wound type, counts were DFU (29), VLU (17), and PU (63).

Baseline characteristics

Baseline characteristics for each wound type (DFU, PU, and VLU) are summarized in Table 1, 2, and 3 respectively. Across all treatment groups, median age ranged from 69 to 77 years. Diabetes was expectedly universal in all DFU cohorts and frequent in other groups; other comorbidities such as cardiovascular disease, peripheral neuropathy, chronic kidney disease, depression, and malignancy were also common. Overall, the cohorts demonstrated considerable heterogeneity in wound severity, chronicity, and comorbidity burden across products and wound types.

Treated performance benchmarks (single-arm)

Among cohorts with more than ten participants, outcomes differed notably across products and wound types. In diabetic foot ulcers (DFU), HAM-A (N=22) and HAM-B (N=11) exhibited comparable 12-week closure rates of 36.4% (95% CI: 17.2–59.3%) in both groups, though HAM-A-treated ulcers required a longer median time to closure (52 vs. 28 days). Early improvement at 4 weeks was observed in 50.0% (95% CI: 15.7–84.3%) of HAM-A-treated DFUs.

In pressure ulcers (PU), HAM-A (N=59) demonstrated a 12-week closure rate of 10.2% (95% CI: 3.8–20.8%) with a median closure time of 35 days [IQR 10], while HAM-B (N=35) achieved a higher closure rate of 22.9% (95% CI: 10.4–40.1%) and a longer median time to closure of 46

days [IQR 16]. Early improvement at 4 weeks was 26.3% (95% CI: 9.1–51.2%) for HAM-A and 20.8% (95% CI: 7.1–42.2%) for HAM-B.

Among venous leg ulcers (VLU), HAM-A (N=38) and HAM-B (N=23) closure rates were 5.3% (95% CI: 0.6–17.7%) and 17.4% (95% CI: 5.0–38.8%), respectively. The median time to closure was shorter for HAM-A (14 days [IQR 7]) than for HAM-B (38 days [IQR 28]). Early improvement at 4 weeks was observed in 7.1% (95% CI: 0.2–33.9%) of HAM-A-treated and 20.0% (95% CI: 0.5–71.6%) of HAM-B-treated VLUs.

Discussion

Single-arm benchmarks describe healing trajectories for patients treated with amniotic membrane allografts under routine care across common chronic wound types. The results of this study show that in a very complex, comorbid study population with large, severe chronic wounds, preliminary benchmarks for healing seem promising. Highlights include over 36% healing rates for DFU patients treated with HAM-A or HAM-B, and almost 23% healing rates for PU patients treated with HAM-B.

These results are contextualized by a real-world study population that exhibited a comorbidity burden and wound characteristics that are frequently excluded from controlled trials. Notable examples include are noted below for groups with N>10 (HAM-A-DFU, HAM-B-DFU, HAM-A-PU, HAM-B-PU, HAM-A-VLU):

- Rates of cardiovascular disease ranging from 70.6-93.1%
- Rates of chronic kidney disease ranging from 25.4-51.7%
- Rates of diabetes ranging from 29.4-50.8% (excluding the DFU cohort)
- Rates of peripheral neuropathy ranging from 29.4-69.0%

- Rates of peripheral arterial disease ranging from 17.5-51.7%
- Rates of malignancy ranging from 11.8-24.1%
- Rates of depression ranging from 29.4-65.5%
- Rates of major amputation ranging from 7-14%

It is notable that no patients were excluded for any of the characteristics above, resulting in a more complex, comorbid population typically seen in RCTs (for example, it is common for patients to be excluded from RCT based on the severity of their cardiovascular disease, chronic kidney disease, and diabetes; cancer is frequently an exclusion criteria). Additionally, patients were not excluded for smoking status or poor clinic follow up. These factors are well-known predictors of delayed wound healing and wound-related complications; the high prevalence of these factors and the heterogeneity of the study population indicate that it is well suited for real-world efficacy of skin substitute allografts.

These multi-etiology results offer pragmatic outcome benchmarks for amniotic membrane allografts in routine clinical practice and motivate opportunities for future controlled efficacy studies in complex, real-world populations that are found in routine clinical practice.

Limitations

Limitations of this study include a single-arm design; modest sample size with sparse subgroups; reliance on routine care settings and documentation; and incomplete capture of 4- and 12-week windows. Additionally, limitations are inherent to retrospective EHR analyses. Residual confounding may persist, e.g., incomplete capture or misclassification of study design elements. Documentation density varies across sites and over time, which can influence outcome ascertainment (e.g., 4-week measurements, confirmation encounters). Some strata are small, leading to imprecision, suppression of rare events, and reliance on descriptive rather than

inferential presentation. These factors warrant cautious interpretation and motivate prospective, comparative research with adequate power, bias control, and adjudicated endpoints.

Clinical and policy implications

These results provide reference values for expected healing under routine care, aid in setting patient and clinician expectations, and identify practice patterns that may influence outcomes (e.g., adherence to compression/offloading). If the direction and magnitude of comparative differences observed in eligible strata persist under the prespecified bias-controlled estimators, findings may inform when to introduce advanced therapy and support coverage considerations for specific wound types. Conversely, attenuated or null differences would encourage more selective use and intensified optimization of standard-of-care components.

Next steps

Operational priorities include completing accrual to meet information thresholds, strengthening capture of other prognostic variables where incomplete, and executing the prespecified propensity-based weighting analyses once overlap and ESS criteria are satisfied. The confirmatory phase will also assess durability of healing, subgroup effects by baseline wound area and duration, and site-level contributors to heterogeneity.

Funding and Role of the Sponsor

This work was supported by Legacy Medical Consultants. The funder had access to de-identified, aggregated data only and had no role in study design, data collection, analysis, and interpretation, or writing of the report.

Competing Interests

All authors declare that they have no competing interests in accordance with journal policy.

Ethics Approval

This retrospective study used de-identified electronic health records under institutional governance. Solutions IRB determined that the research is exempt under 45 CFR 46.104(d)(4) (secondary research using identifiable private information or biospecimens for which consent is not required). Because data were de-identified prior to analysis, informed consent and HIPAA authorization were waived. The determination letter (Protocol Number: 0878, Date: 8/12/2025) is on file with the Sponsor. All activities followed the prespecified protocol and Interim Statistical Analysis Plan and adhered to contractual privacy protections.

Data and Code Availability

Data sharing is governed by site data-use agreements and privacy safeguards.

Registration and Protocol Access

This work is registered at [ClinicalTrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov) as an observational, retrospective EHR cohort (NCT07223281). The registration reflects non-interventional status (no assignment to treatment) and specifies primary and secondary outcomes consistent with the prespecified protocol.

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Disclaimer

The content is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily represent the official views of any institution.

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Tables

Table 1. Baseline characteristics by treatment group (DFU)

Characteristic	HAM-A	HAM-B	Total
N	16	13	29
Age mean \pm SD	69.2 \pm 10.1	71.2 \pm 7.5	—
Age median [IQR]	71.0 [61.2, 75.8]	69.0 [66.0, 73.0]	—
Baseline area (cm ²), median [IQR]	2.2 [0.0, 4.2]	3.0 [1.6, 10.0]	—
Baseline duration (days), median [IQR]	60.0 [58.0, 77.0]	237.0 [172.5, 301.5]	—
Diabetes, n (%)	16 (100.0%)	13 (100.0%)	29 (100.0%)
Depression, n (%)	11 (68.8%)	8 (61.5%)	19 (65.5%)
Cardiovascular disease, n (%)	14 (87.5%)	13 (100.0%)	27 (93.1%)
Chronic kidney disease, n (%)	7 (43.8%)	8 (61.5%)	15 (51.7%)
Malignancy, n (%)	4 (25.0%)	3 (23.1%)	7 (24.1%)
Venous insufficiency, n (%)	4 (25.0%)	1 (7.7%)	5 (17.2%)
Peripheral neuropathy, n (%)	11 (68.8%)	9 (69.2%)	20 (69.0%)
Peripheral arterial disease, n (%)	7 (43.8%)	8 (61.5%)	15 (51.7%)
Systemic antibiotics, n (%)	6 (37.5%)	9 (69.2%)	15 (51.7%)
Systemic corticosteroids, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (15.4%)	2 (6.9%)
Immunosuppressants, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (7.7%)	1 (3.4%)
Antidiabetic medications, n (%)	13 (81.2%)	13 (100.0%)	26 (89.7%)
Chemotherapy agents, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (7.7%)	1 (3.4%)
Anticoagulants, n (%)	8 (50.0%)	7 (53.8%)	15 (51.7%)
Hyperbaric oxygen therapy, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Hospitalization, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Emergency visit, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Major amputation, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Minor amputation, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Revascularization of lower extremity, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Venous ablation, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Wound related systemic infection, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)

Ambulatory status: NA, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Ambulatory status: Unknown, n (%)	3 (18.8%)	4 (30.8%)	7 (24.1%)
Ambulatory status: Non-ambulatory, n (%)	3 (18.8%)	1 (7.7%)	4 (13.8%)
Ambulatory status: With assistive device, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (30.8%)	4 (13.8%)
Ambulatory status: Independent, n (%)	3 (18.8%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (10.3%)
Ambulatory status: Wheelchair, n (%)	1 (6.2%)	1 (7.7%)	2 (6.9%)
Ambulatory status: Bedbound, n (%)	1 (6.2%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.4%)
Smoking status: Current smoker, n (%)	8 (50.0%)	4 (30.8%)	12 (41.4%)
Smoking status: Former smoker, n (%)	2 (12.5%)	6 (46.2%)	8 (27.6%)
Smoking status: NA, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Smoking status: Never smoker, n (%)	1 (6.2%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.4%)
Living status: Home, n (%)	7 (43.8%)	9 (69.2%)	16 (55.2%)
Living status: NA, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Living status: Assisted living, n (%)	2 (12.5%)	2 (15.4%)	4 (13.8%)
Living status: SNF, n (%)	2 (12.5%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.9%)
Living status: Unknown, n (%)	2 (12.5%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.9%)
Bmi mean \pm SD	42.6 \pm 25.3	53.1 \pm 38.7	—
Bmi median [IQR]	35.3 [25.1, 50.0]	37.4 [31.1, 67.3]	—
A1c mean \pm SD	7.8 \pm 1.2	8.1 \pm 2.9	—
A1c median [IQR]	8.4 [7.4, 8.5]	6.9 [6.4, 9.2]	—

Table 2. Baseline characteristics by treatment group (PU)

Characteristic	HAM-A	HAM-B	HAM-C	Total
N	33	28	2	63
Age mean \pm SD	69.0 \pm 19.2	70.0 \pm 17.1	70.5 \pm 2.1	—
Age median [IQR]	75.0 [66.0, 80.0]	72.5 [62.8, 84.5]	70.5 [69.8, 71.2]	—
Baseline area (cm ²), median [IQR]	4.2 [0.5, 21.0]	9.6 [3.9, 25.9]	16.6 [10.3, 22.9]	
Baseline duration (days), median [IQR]	252.0 [79.0, 485.8]	192.0 [102.8, 338.5]	214.0 [130.0, 298.0]	
Diabetes, n (%)	21 (63.6%)	11 (39.3%)	0 (0.0%)	32 (50.8%)
Depression, n (%)	17 (51.5%)	13 (46.4%)	1 (50.0%)	31 (49.2%)
Cardiovascular disease, n (%)	25 (75.8%)	23 (82.1%)	1 (50.0%)	49 (77.8%)
Chronic kidney disease, n (%)	10 (30.3%)	6 (21.4%)	0 (0.0%)	16 (25.4%)
Malignancy, n (%)	9 (27.3%)	3 (10.7%)	0 (0.0%)	12 (19.0%)
Venous insufficiency, n (%)	7 (21.2%)	4 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)	11 (17.5%)
Peripheral neuropathy, n (%)	13 (39.4%)	10 (35.7%)	0 (0.0%)	23 (36.5%)
Peripheral arterial disease, n (%)	6 (18.2%)	4 (14.3%)	1 (50.0%)	11 (17.5%)
Systemic antibiotics, n (%)	13 (39.4%)	9 (32.1%)	0 (0.0%)	22 (34.9%)
Systemic corticosteroids, n (%)	2 (6.1%)	4 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (9.5%)
Immunosuppressants, n (%)	1 (3.0%)	2 (7.1%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (4.8%)
Antidiabetic medications, n (%)	13 (39.4%)	5 (17.9%)	0 (0.0%)	18 (28.6%)
Chemotherapy agents, n (%)	2 (6.1%)	1 (3.6%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (4.8%)
Anticoagulants, n (%)	6 (18.2%)	9 (32.1%)	0 (0.0%)	15 (23.8%)
Hyperbaric oxygen therapy, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Hospitalization, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Emergency visit, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Major amputation, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Minor amputation, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Revascularization of lower extremity, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Venous ablation, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Wound related systemic infection, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Ambulatory status: NA, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Ambulatory status: Non-ambulatory, n (%)	2 (6.1%)	7 (25.0%)	2 (100.0%)	11 (17.5%)

Ambulatory status: Unknown, n (%)	4 (12.1%)	6 (21.4%)	0 (0.0%)	10 (15.9%)
Ambulatory status: Bedbound, n (%)	4 (12.1%)	3 (10.7%)	0 (0.0%)	7 (11.1%)
Ambulatory status: Wheelchair, n (%)	4 (12.1%)	2 (7.1%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (9.5%)
Ambulatory status: With assistive device, n (%)	2 (6.1%)	2 (7.1%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (6.3%)
Ambulatory status: Independent, n (%)	2 (6.1%)	1 (3.6%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (4.8%)
Smoking status: NA, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Smoking status: Current smoker, n (%)	10 (30.3%)	4 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)	14 (22.2%)
Smoking status: Former smoker, n (%)	5 (15.2%)	7 (25.0%)	1 (50.0%)	13 (20.6%)
Smoking status: Never smoker, n (%)	1 (3.0%)	4 (14.3%)	1 (50.0%)	6 (9.5%)
Living status: Home, n (%)	21 (63.6%)	20 (71.4%)	0 (0.0%)	41 (65.1%)
Living status: SNF, n (%)	4 (12.1%)	4 (14.3%)	2 (100.0%)	10 (15.9%)
Living status: NA, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Living status: Assisted living, n (%)	1 (3.0%)	1 (3.6%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.2%)
Living status: Hospice, n (%)	1 (3.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.6%)
Bmi mean \pm SD	27.5 \pm 7.4	31.8 \pm 12.7	22.4 \pm 2.5	—
Bmi median [IQR]	24.9 [22.6, 35.6]	29.6 [21.8, 37.8]	22.4 [21.5, 23.2]	—
A1c mean \pm SD	—	6.1 \pm 0.4	—	—
A1c median [IQR]	8.2 [8.2, 8.2]	6.1 [5.9, 6.2]	—	—

Table 3. Baseline characteristics by treatment group (VLU)

Characteristic	HAM-A	HAM-B	HAM-C	Total
N	9	7	1	17
Age mean \pm SD	71.7 \pm 10.2	78.0 \pm 8.2	—	—
Age median [IQR]	76.0 [67.0, 77.0]	77.0 [73.0, 83.0]	70.0 [70.0, 70.0]	—
Baseline area (cm ²), median [IQR]	13.5 [0.2, 33.0]	27.0 [9.2, 79.9]		
Baseline duration (days), median [IQR]	368.0	366.0	220.0	
Diabetes, n (%)	1 (11.1%)	3 (42.9%)	1 (100.0%)	5 (29.4%)
Depression, n (%)	4 (44.4%)	1 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (29.4%)
Cardiovascular disease, n (%)	7 (77.8%)	4 (57.1%)	1 (100.0%)	12 (70.6%)
Chronic kidney disease, n (%)	3 (33.3%)	3 (42.9%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (35.3%)
Malignancy, n (%)	2 (22.2%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (11.8%)
Venous insufficiency, n (%)	7 (77.8%)	5 (71.4%)	1 (100.0%)	13 (76.5%)
Peripheral neuropathy, n (%)	4 (44.4%)	1 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (29.4%)
Peripheral arterial disease, n (%)	3 (33.3%)	3 (42.9%)	1 (100.0%)	7 (41.2%)
Systemic antibiotics, n (%)	5 (55.6%)	5 (71.4%)	0 (0.0%)	10 (58.8%)
Systemic corticosteroids, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Immunosuppressants, n (%)	1 (11.1%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (5.9%)
Antidiabetic medications, n (%)	1 (11.1%)	3 (42.9%)	1 (100.0%)	5 (29.4%)
Chemotherapy agents, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Anticoagulants, n (%)	2 (22.2%)	3 (42.9%)	1 (100.0%)	6 (35.3%)
Hyperbaric oxygen therapy, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Hospitalization, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Emergency visit, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Major amputation, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Minor amputation, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Revascularization of lower extremity, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Venous ablation, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Wound related systemic infection, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Ambulatory status: NA, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Ambulatory status: Wheelchair, n (%)	4 (44.4%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (23.5%)
Ambulatory status: Independent, n (%)	1 (11.1%)	1 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (11.8%)
Ambulatory status: Unknown, n (%)	1 (11.1%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (100.0%)	2 (11.8%)

Ambulatory status: Non-ambulatory, n (%)	1 (11.1%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (5.9%)
Ambulatory status: With assistive device, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (5.9%)
Smoking status: NA, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Smoking status: Current smoker, n (%)	3 (33.3%)	2 (28.6%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (29.4%)
Smoking status: Former smoker, n (%)	1 (11.1%)	2 (28.6%)	1 (100.0%)	4 (23.5%)
Smoking status: Never smoker, n (%)	2 (22.2%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (11.8%)
Living status: Home, n (%)	3 (33.3%)	5 (71.4%)	1 (100.0%)	9 (52.9%)
Living status: NA, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Living status: SNF, n (%)	2 (22.2%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (11.8%)
Living status: Unknown, n (%)	2 (22.2%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (11.8%)
Bmi mean \pm SD	36.3 \pm 8.4	67.8 \pm 41.3	—	—
Bmi median [IQR]	37.4 [32.0, 41.7]	67.8 [53.2, 82.4]	—	—
A1c mean \pm SD	—	—	—	—
A1c median [IQR]	9.5 [9.5, 9.5]	7.2 [7.2, 7.2]	—	—

Table 4. Day 84 (Week 12) healing and early improvement at approximately 4 weeks by wound type and treatment group

Indication	Product Brand	Population N	Closed by 12w N (%) [95% CI]	Days to closure median [IQR]	Early improvement at 4w n (%) [95% CI]	12w PAR (%) among open (mean±SD; median [IQR])
DFU	HAM-A	22	8 (36.4% [17.2%, 59.3%])	52 [34]	4 (50.0% [15.7%, 84.3%])	58.7±35.8; 65.2 [43.7]
DFU	HAM-B	11	4 (36.4% [10.9%, 69.2%])	28 [23]	0 (0.0% [0.0%, 70.8%])	2.8±48.9; 7.6 [40.6]
PU	HAM-C	3	0 (0.0% [0.0%, 70.8%])	NA	2 (100.0% [15.8%, 100.0%])	67.2±12.4; 67.2 [8.8]
PU	HAM-A	59	6 (10.2% [3.8%, 20.8%])	35 [10]	5 (26.3% [9.1%, 51.2%])	27.7±78.7; 43.4 [59.8]
PU	HAM-B	35	8 (22.9% [10.4%, 40.1%])	46 [16]	5 (20.8% [7.1%, 42.2%])	-76.5±384.3; 30.6 [68.5]
VLU	HAM-C	1	0 (0.0% [0.0%, 97.5%])	NA	NA	NA
VLU	HAM-A	38	2 (5.3% [0.6%, 17.7%])	14 [7]	1 (7.1% [0.2%, 33.9%])	-45.9±77.0; -21.5 [87.9]
VLU	HAM-B	23	4 (17.4% [5.0%, 38.8%])	38 [28]	1 (20.0% [0.5%, 71.6%])	-7.8±33.1; 0.0 [30.0]